

Study of Transition and Non-Transition Metal Complexes with 3-Amino-2-Benzoylbenzofuran

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The complexes of 3-amino-2-benzoylbenzofuran, (L), with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) have been synthesized and characterised on the basis of chemical analysis, conductance, magnetic measurements, electronic and infrared spectral studies. Co(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes are found to possess tetrahedral structure whereas Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes exhibit polymeric, octahedral structures and Cu(II) complex undergoes Jahn-Teller distortion.

BENZOFURAN derivatives are well known as biologically and pharmacologically important compounds¹⁻³. There are reports on metal complexes of benzofurans and their derivatives⁴⁻⁷, but no information on metal complexes derived from 3-amino-2-benzoylbenzofuran is available. The present communication is a part of a programme to study such complexes and deals with the synthesis and structural features of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes of 3-amino-2-benzoylbenzofuran.

Experimental

Materials: The chemicals used in this investigation were of analytical grade.

Ligand: 3-Amino-2-benzoylbenzofuran was prepared by the known⁸ procedure.

Preparation of the complexes: Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Hg(II) complexes were prepared by treating the hot ethanolic solution of the ligand with ethanolic solution of corresponding metal chloride in 1:1 molar ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 1-2 hr. The solution was then reduced to a smaller volume on water bath, cooled and treated with petroleum ether (60-80°) to isolate the respective metal complexes, except Cu(II) complex, for which the solution was concentrated to a pasty mass and treated with solvent ether in excess. The respective solid complexes were filtered and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂ in a desiccator.

Cd(II) complex: Ethanolic solutions of the metal chloride (CdCl₂·2.5H₂O) and the ligand, in molar ratio 1:1, were mixed with vigorous stirring. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The precipitation of the complex was aided by further digestion on water-bath for about 1 hr. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with hot ethanol and dried in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

All the complexes were further purified by Soxhlet.

Chemical analysis: The complexes were analysed for metal and halogen by standard methods. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl method⁹.

Physical measurements: The molar conductance of the complexes were measured, using ELICO CM-82 conductivity bridge with a cell having cell constant of 1.0 cm⁻¹. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance at room temperature, using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant. The ir spectra of the ligand and the complexes in nujol mull were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 297, in 4000-600 cm⁻¹ region. The far ir spectra of the complexes in nujol mull were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 599 spectrophotometer using CsI plates. The electronic spectra were recorded on ELICO model CL-24 spectrophotometer in 900-340 nm region in DMF.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are soluble in common organic solvents, except Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes which are soluble in DMF and DMSO. The molar conductance of all the complexes, except Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes, in DMF (10⁻³ M) fall in the range of 1-12 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹, indicating that they are non-electrolytes¹⁰.

In the case of Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes, the observed conductivity values (Table 1) in DMF (10⁻³ M) indicate the complexes to be 1:1 electrolytes¹¹.

Magnetic moment: The magnetic moments of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes calculated from the corrected magnetic susceptibilities (at room temperature) are given in Table 1. The observed magnetic moment, 4.9 B.M., of the Co(II) complex is higher than the 'spin only' value of three unpaired electrons and is considered to be due to large orbital contribution in a tetrahedral environment. The magnetic moment, 3.1 B.M., observed for the Ni(II) complex is within the range of 2.9-3.4 B.M. reported¹² for octahedral complex.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND CONDUCTANCE FOR Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) AND Hg(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	Metal% Found (Calcd.)	N% Found (Calcd.)	Cl% Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.	Molecular conductivity $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$
CoLCl ₂	15.98 (16.06)	3.85 (3.81)	18.97 (19.35)	4.9	3.45
NiLCl ₂ .H ₂ O	14.92 (15.26)	3.53 (3.64)	18.65 (18.46)	3.1	66.51
CuLCl ₂	17.41 (17.1)	3.68 (3.77)	19.29 (19.11)	1.9	90.01
ZnLCl ₂	17.29 (17.51)	3.46 (3.74)	18.83 (19.01)	—	12.01
CdLCl ₂ .H ₂ O	25.78 (25.64)	3.92 (3.19)	16.29 (16.19)	—	1.42
HgLCl ₂	39.72 (39.43)	3.05 (2.76)	13.73 (13.96)	—	3.32

The magnetic moment value of the Cu(II) complex lies within the range of 1.67-1.90 B.M., which indicates that the complex does not involve spin-spin interaction. However, the polymeric nature of the complex cannot be precluded, as the polymeric complexes with no spin interaction are known in literature^{13,14}. Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) being d¹⁰ ions show diamagnetism.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes are characterised by the band maxima around 660 nm with a shoulder at 590 nm, 725 nm - 675 nm, and 680 nm, respectively. All these complexes display an absorption peak centered around 410 nm. Considering the intensity of this band, we have attributed it to the L→M charge transfer band.

It is known¹⁵ that Co(II) complex in tetrahedral environment exhibits a high intensity multiplet (600-700 nm) due to ⁴A₂→⁴T₁(P) transition. The observed band maxima lie very well in the region of tetrahedral configuration. The Ni(II) complex exhibits a spectrum typical of octahedral environment. It is documented in literature¹⁵ that d⁸ system, viz. Ni(II), displays three bands in the 400-1400 nm region. These have been attributed to various transitions. The limit of our spectrophotometer does not allow the location of the band due

to ⁴A₂→⁴T₂ transition. However, the ⁴A₂→⁴T₁(F) transition for the complex under consideration occurs in the region 725-675 nm as a split band. The splitting envisaged in the transition may be due to the spin-orbital coupling. The transition due to ⁴A₂→⁴T₁(P) has been overlaid by the high intensity charge transfer band around 410 nm. It is evident from literature¹⁵ that the Cu(II) complexes in an octahedral environment show a broad band around 800 nm due to ²E_g→²T_{2g}. This is highly sensitive to Jahn-Teller distortion and shifts hypsochromically with an increase in the tetragonal distortion. The observed band in the region 680 nm can be considered to be due to ²E_g→²T_{2g} and the hypsochromic shift indicates the distortion brought about in the complex due to Jahn-Teller phenomenon.

Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) being d¹⁰ ions do not show d-d transitions. Therefore, the stereochemistry of their complexes cannot be derived from their electronic spectra. The information on their structure has, therefore, been derived from infrared measurements only.

Infrared spectra: Selected infrared frequencies along with their tentative assignments are listed in Table 2. In the ir spectra of Ni(II) and Cd(II) complexes, broad band around 3500-3450 cm⁻¹ due to ν(OH) of water molecule appears. On heating the complexes above 110°, the water molecule is lost showing that it is lattice held and not coordinated. The bands observed in the region 3400-3100 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the ν(NH) vibrations. The coordination of the metal through nitrogen should cause splitting of these bands and decrease in their intensities¹⁶, or shifting of these bands towards low frequency side. The Co(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Zn(II) complexes of 3-amino-2-benzoylbenzofuran show neither such splitting nor shifting towards low frequency side, indicating non-involvement of NH₂ group in bond formation. In the case of the Ni(II) and Hg(II) complexes, ν(NH) band shifts towards low frequency side, indicating the involvement of NH₂ group in bond formation.

In the case of 3-amino-2-benzoylbenzofuran complexes, the ligand band observed at 1625 cm⁻¹

TABLE 2—SELECTED INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF THE LIGAND AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES

Ligand (L)	CoLCl ₂	NiLCl ₂ .H ₂ O	CuLCl ₂	ZnLCl ₂	CdLCl ₂ .H ₂ O	HgLCl ₂	Assignment
—	—	3500-3450b	—	—	3500-3450b	—	ν(OH)
3418mb	3520b	3400w	3430m	3430w	3440s	3380ms	—
3280mb	3380b	3280w	3320b	3320w	3330s	3270ms	ν(N-H)
3170mb	—	3160w	—	3180b	3170w	3160w	—
1625s	1610ms	1620ms	1690mb	1615ms	1620s	1610ms	ν(C=O)
1250w	1245w	1250w	1245vw	1240w	1250w	1250w	—
1170mb	1165mb	1170b	1145b	1175s	1180s	1175ms	ν(C-O-C)
—	—	—	—	1150sh	1165sh	—	ν(M-O) furan ring oxygen
—	490m	—	505ms	490m	500ms	—	ν(M-O)
—	300w	320w	300s	290w	262w	325w	ν(M-N)
—	—	235ms	—	—	—	420s	ν(M-Cl)
—	330w	—	—	230w	220w	290s	ν(M-Cl) _b
—	—	282w	280w	—	—	—	—

s = strong, w = weak, m = medium, ms = medium strong, mb = medium broad, vw = very weak, b = bridging, sh = shoulder.

due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ has been shifted towards lower frequency side in all the complexes. This shift is suggestive of coordination of $(\text{C}=\text{O})$ group through oxygen¹⁷.

The ligand band observed in the range 1075-1250 cm^{-1} has been attributed to the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C})$ mode in view of previous assignments^{18,19}. This band shifts towards the lower frequency side in the case of $\text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ complexes indicating the involvement of furan ring oxygen in bond formation, whereas in the case of the $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ complexes no such shift is observed indicating non-involvement of furan ring oxygen in bond formation. In the complexes of $\text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$, a very sharp band observed at $500 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is the band involving the metal and furan oxygen linkage^{20,21}.

The low frequency bands in the range 325-260 cm^{-1} , not observed in the ligand spectrum, are assigned to $\text{M}-\text{O}$ stretching vibration in all the complexes and agree well with previous assignments^{22,23}. The bands observed at 420 cm^{-1} and 235 cm^{-1} in the spectra of $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ complexes respectively, have been assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ vibrations²⁴. The bands in the range of 330-220 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ vibrations²⁴⁻²⁶ in all the complexes except $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ complexes. In the case of $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ complexes, which exhibit polymeric nature, a band around 280 cm^{-1} is assigned to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})_b$ which agrees well with previous assignments²⁴.

In view of the spectral observations taken together with analytical data, magnetic moments and molar conductance, we propose the following structures for the complexes.

M = $\text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$.

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